

CITING SILENCES: FINDING A HISTORY ‘OUTSIDE’ THE ARCHIVE

by

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DEDICATION

For Michael Brinkman

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This thesis examines how the authorizing norms of Euro-Western historiography—organized by white supremacy—produce and maintain silences, excluding entire communities from historical narrative. Trouillot identifies silences as structural to historical narrative, operating at every moment of historical production. Yet the exit from silence appears guarded by the same norms that created it.

Derrida's iterability shows that no context can be saturated and no meaning foreclosed. The archive is inherently open to future interpretation. Butler's topology of power reveals that these norms produce a constitutive outside, a zone of what cannot be said as history, that is structurally necessary for the inside to cohere but always threatens to destabilize it. Working within the authorizing norms reinscribes them. Transgression is necessary.

Hartman's critical fabulation demonstrates a practice that neither fills the silence with fiction nor accepts the archive's violence as final. Working through the archival figure of Venus—a young African girl who appears in the historical record only through the trial of the slave-ship captain implicated in her death—Hartman cites the silence, lifting it from the context the archive imposed, where it served the ends of white supremacy, and placing it in a new context that exposes the violence. This thesis develops the hauntological *irrealis* to name the register this practice requires: a mode that neither asserts what cannot be asserted nor concedes the loss to the authorizing norms. The hauntological *irrealis* offers a mode of textual

accountability to the silenced rather than to the evidentiary norms that produced their silences.

Hartman's work serves as an existence proof for transgressive historiography.

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INTRODUCTION¹

This thesis examines how the authorizing norms² of Euro-Western historicity—the rules that govern what counts as history, who counts as an historian, what counts as evidence—produce and maintain exclusions of entire communities from historical narrative. Archives created by hostile or indifferent institutions—by those who already have their hands on the scepter—repeat, reiterate, the stories and the rules, creating “standardized methods” that act as gatekeepers to keep out those deemed unworthy, whose existence is criminalized. Many stories can be lost forever. Those who are left out are “silenced”, actively or systemically excluded from the archive. Black studies has provided us with robust theoretical and practical scholarship, but the problems of silencing are not limited to the Black community. Black, queer, disabled, working-class, and many other communities are excluded from the archive. And, of course, “the major systems of oppression are interlocking.”³

“White supremacy is the unnamed political system that has made the modern world what it is today.”⁴ The racial contract is not an aberration of the historiographic apparatus but a

¹ As a white, queer, non-historian working at the intersection of philosophy, law, and government, I acknowledge that I have benefited in many ways from the power structures that produce the silences I am writing about. In large part it is for this reason that I have chosen to write about the theoretical structures involved and how they can be transgressed, rather than attempting to deal with specific silenced events and lives in detail. My interest in historical silences began in a course on race, coloniality, and empire, where I first encountered Trouillot. The concept of silences both fascinated me as a philosopher and disturbed me as a person. I note that among the theorists this thesis engages, Hartman and Trouillot write from within the histories they analyze; Derrida and Butler largely do not self-situate in this way. Positionality statements sit uneasily in philosophical writing, which has traditionally claimed to speak from no particular position. But this is one of philosophy’s authorizing norms; there is no nowhere from which to speak.

² I use 'authorizing norms' throughout this thesis to describe the regulatory apparatus that determines what counts as history, adapting Butler's 'regulatory norms' from the domain of gender to the domain of historiography.

³ Combahee River Collective, “The Combahee River Collective Statement,” BlackPast.Org, April 1977, <https://blackpast.org/african-american-history/combahee-river-collective-statement-1977/>.

⁴ Charles W. Mills, *The Racial Contract* (Cornell University Press, 2022), 1.

structuring condition of it. When the authors I engage with speak of power, this power is white supremacy. When I speak of what the archive wants to maintain or of the authorizing norms of historiography, these norms—this archival “desire”—are not arbitrary; they are expressions of white supremacy. When I speak of the outside that defines the identity of the inside, that identity is white identity.⁵ Black, queer, disabled, working-class, and many other communities are excluded from the archive, by an apparatus organized by white supremacy even where the excluded are not all racialized in the same way.

This thesis grew out of questions first raised in Dr. Kerry Sinanan’s graduate seminar, “Unsettling Race, Coloniality and Empire in the Long 19th Century” at the University of Texas at San Antonio in the fall of 2022, in which we read works by both Michel-Rolph Trouillot and Saidiya Hartman. Reading Michel-Rolph Trouillot’s *Silencing the Past: Power and the Production of History*, I became interested in the philosophical nature of historical silences. I thought theoretical understanding of silences — bringing together Trouillot’s structure and continental theory — might disclose more ways to ‘unsilence’ and what that even means. Derrida’s “Signature, Event, Context” led me to Butler, initially for performativity and subversive bodily acts, but Timothy R. Pauketat’s *An Archaeology of the Cosmos*⁶ pointed me to *Bodies That Matter*. I immediately saw a close connection between Butler’s description of the gendered/sexed body and Trouillot’s structure of historical narrative. The concept of the hauntological unreal grew out of Hartman’s reference to the subjunctive, Derrida’s

⁵ For Trouillot and Hartman, white supremacy is expressly named. Derrida does not name the power he is responding to in the texts I engage. Butler’s central target in *Bodies That Matter* is heteronormativity, but they engage racial power throughout—including in the chapters “Gender is Burning” (engaging Jennie Livingston’s *Paris Is Burning*) and “Passing, Queering” (engaging Nella Larsen’s *Passing*)—and the topology of constitutive outside that I draw on is developed in part through their reading of racialized bodies.

⁶ *An Archaeology of the Cosmos: Rethinking Agency and Religion in Ancient America* (Routledge, 2013).

“hauntology”, and a deep personal interest in linguistics and how grammar and thought are connected.

Bringing Trouillot and Hartman, two Black writers working in history and literature, together with Derrida and Butler, two of the most prominent contemporary continental philosophers, is itself a methodological commitment. The disciplinary norms that segregate Black studies and decolonial thought from continental philosophy are the same authorizing norms that white supremacy uses to exclude narratives from history, the same authorizing norms that are the subject of this thesis. But Black and colonial experiences are fundamentally intertwined with the European thought that sets them apart. As this thesis will describe, they are the constitutive outside that defines the inside and they are therefore conditions of possibility for European theory. What I work out here is a synthesis that is not incidental; it is constitutive, and it is offered against the segregations that would have made it harder to see.

The path to understanding silences starts from Michel-Rolph Trouillot’s identification of them as structural to historical narrative. Trouillot diagnoses the structure of silencing across four moments of historical production and demonstrates that silences are produced by the wielding of material power, not by accident or oversight. He shows where silences enter, but the exit appears to remain guarded by the same norms that created the silences.

Jacques Derrida shows us that the authorizing norms cannot fix the contexts they purport to govern. No set of criteria can fully determine what a source means, what an archive preserves, or what a narrative concludes, because context is unsaturable. Judith Butler shows that these norms produce a constitutive outside, a zone of what cannot be said as history, that is not merely excluded but structurally necessary for the inside to be identifiable. But this outside always threatens to destabilize the inside. Together, Derrida and Butler show that the authorizing norms

are not the neutral rules they claim, but constitutive boundary-making, there to maintain the identity of the archive. Working within them always reinscribes them; transgressing⁷ them can destabilize them.

Saidiya Hartman's critical fabulation exploits the instability of the context. Her critical fabulation, rather than confining itself to evidence or slipping into fiction, holds open a place that the archive violently closed. Her practice is accountable to the violence, not to the authorizing norms. Critical fabulation is an existence proof that transgressive history is possible, not a template. What I term the hauntological unrealis, a writing in a mode that neither asserts what cannot be asserted nor concedes the loss to the authorizing norms, is the register this requires. Hartman demonstrates that silences can be removed from the context the archive imposed, put in quotation marks—" "—and cited in a new context that exposes the violence rather than reinscribing it.

Chapter 1, "Silence as Structure", establishes silences as structural to historical narrative through Trouillot. Using his *Silencing the Past*, the chapter maps the four moments when silences enter historical production and shows that silencing is produced by material power. Chapter 2, "The Archive Repeats", uses Derrida's *Limited Inc* to introduce *iterability* and show the authorizing norms cannot fix meaning or foreclose other readings. It then uses Derrida's *Archive Fever* to explain how the archive's repetition compulsion works against its own authority. Chapter 3, "Topologies of Power", develops Butler's topology of the body from *Bodies That Matter* and applies it to history. It discusses how authorizing norms are constitutive

⁷ I use 'transgress' throughout to describe practices that cross or violate the boundaries established by the authorizing norms. Butler uses the term occasionally but prefers 'subversive repetition' or 'resignification'; the difference is that Butler emphasizes working within the norm by citing it unfaithfully, whereas 'transgression' as I use it foregrounds the crossing and disruption of the boundary itself.

boundary-work that create the inside yet are structurally threatened by the *constitutive outside*. Chapter 4, “Citing Silences”, shows how Hartman’s work of critical fabulation, as she describes it in “Venus in Two Acts”, is a practice that works within the instability established in the preceding chapters. Using Derrida’s *Cinders* and Palmer’s work on linguistic modality, it develops the hauntological irrealis of this practice and suggests its application to other transgressive historiographic practices, offering the hauntological irrealis as a mode of textual accountability that names what the archive foreclosed without filling its silences.

CHAPTER 1: SILENCE AS STRUCTURE

“[N]ot even the dead will be safe from the enemy, if he is victorious. And this enemy has not ceased to be victorious.”

—Walter Benjamin (Thesis VI)

What goes into historical narrative and what stays out is not a neutral or scientific decision and the consequences are not mere absences of evidence in the past but movements of power in the present. Historical actors include—consciously or not—certain stories today in what they consider to be “true history”, whether academic or popular.

Michel-Rolph Trouillot, a Haitian historian and anthropologist whose own national history is among those silenced by Euro-Western historiography, dealt directly with the French colonization of Haiti and centuries of enslavement, culminating in the only major successful revolution by enslaved people in history—a revolution that has been largely successfully silenced in the European and American academy and in history as taught in the classrooms of white-dominated society. Trouillot’s work *Silencing the Past: Power and the Production of History* is a direct confrontation with that silencing and an analysis of it. In this thesis, his work establishes the structure of silences and locates their origin in white supremacy and settler colonialism. The chapter proceeds in three movements: first, “Trouillot’s Narrative as Dialectic” establishes the structure of narrative as a dialectic of mentions and silences; then “Where Silences Enter the Narrative” explains where silences enter and through what mechanisms; finally, “Trouillot’s Two Kinds of History” begins the discussion of what actually happened versus what is said to have happened.

Trouillot identified how historical narratives⁸ are made up of mentions and silences⁹—those things said, and those things unsaid or unsayable. The unsaid is what could be mentioned but is not; the unsayable is what the authorizing norms foreclose from intelligibility, a distinction that will be developed in Chapter 3. As a simple point of communication, we could not possibly mention everything and in the case of history, as with every other form of narrative, something is always missing.¹⁰ While some things may be unsaid for mere convenience or style, I am not concerned here with the mundane silences.¹¹

Trouillot's Narrative as Dialectic

Mentions and silences are in a relationship that is constantly in flux. As one thing is mentioned, other things are silenced, at least relatively. As one thing is emphasized, another is de-emphasized. Trouillot explains this through a dialectic, where mentions and silences are in opposition as a thesis and antithesis. The synthesis of the mentions and silences is the historical narrative.¹² This dialectic is never stable and never finished. Even when Trouillot refers to the "in the final instance",¹³ he clarifies that this is not a final telos but a point, not necessarily following

⁸ Really, *all* narratives, but I'm only concerned here with historical narratives. For the reasons developed in Chapter 2, perhaps all narratives are historical narratives.

⁹ Michel-Rolph Trouillot, *Silencing the Past: Power and the Production of History* (Beacon Press, 2015), 48.

¹⁰ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 49.

¹¹ Though, it is important to note that they may become insidious over time and silences may hide as mundane in any case, and, to the extent that everything may matter to someone, it may be that no silences are ever truly mundane. See note 29 below.

¹² Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 48.

¹³ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 26.

any particular chronology, at which “[r]etrospective significance itself is produced”, that is when history is made, when the original actors and acts mentioned and silenced who were on the stage are referred to and given their historical importance. Despite the word “retrospective”, this can even be prospective.¹⁴

Moreover, these historical narratives can then become a form of act, something that can then be commented on and mentioned or silenced itself. Something that can lead people to action by inspiring or enraging them. Trouillot’s focus is on the structure of silencing rather than on the performative effects of narrative, though he gestures at this in his discussions of strikers and of Henry I.¹⁵

Examples of narratives that have moved others to action include The 1619 Project,¹⁶ which created significant controversy and inspired policy at all levels both in line with the author’s intent and as a reaction to it; and Bartolomé de las Casas’s *Brevísima relación de la destrucción de las Indias*,¹⁷ an historical testimony that has had both immediate and continuing political impacts across centuries. The 1619 Project was explicitly intended to be radically interventionist. Las Casas’s testimony was intended to be a strictly bounded communique to

¹⁴ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 59. Trouillot gives the example here of Henry I (of Haiti) killing Sans Souci and erasing him “from his future”.

¹⁵ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 23–24. See also note 13 above.

¹⁶ Nikole Hannah-Jones, “The 1619 Project,” *The New York Times*, August 14, 2019, <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2019/08/14/magazine/1619-america-slavery.html>.

¹⁷ Bartolomé de Las Casas, *Brevísima relación de la destrucción de las Indias*, ed. José Miguel Martínez Torrejón, Biblioteca Virtual Miguel de Cervantes (Universidad de Alicante, 2006), <https://www.cervantesvirtual.com/obra/brevsima-relacin-de-la-destruccin-de-las-indias-0/>.

Prince Philip (later Phillip II of Spain) that escaped the author's and the Spanish Crown's control.¹⁸

There are also narratives that were themselves acts, i.e. performative historical acts in narrative form. Of course, all historical narrative is performative at one level in that it inscribes history. Here, I refer to narratives that are intended to be performative acts in some other way. For example, Luther's "95 Theses",¹⁹ were intended as an account of wrongs and a call for debate, but not likely for wider publication. As a call for debate according to usual academic customs, they were performative. However, they had much broader impact across centuries. Another example would be the South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission Report, which narrated (the "truth" part) and performed (national reconciliation), while at the same time it had wide-ranging impact both domestically and internationally well beyond these purposes.²⁰

In these ways, Trouillot's dialectic becomes more Hegelian²¹, with each narrative affecting both future narratives and future acts and some narratives being themselves acts *in*

¹⁸ This escaping of the author's control is something I will deal with extensively in succeeding chapters.

¹⁹ Martin Luther, "Disputatio pro declaratione virtutis indulgentiarum," in *D. Martin Luthers Werke : Kritische Gesamtausgabe* (Hermann Böhlaus Nachfolger, 1883), 1:233–38, <http://archive.org/details/dmartinlutherswe11luth>.

²⁰ Truth and Reconciliation Commission, "Truth and Reconciliation Commission of South Africa Report," Truth and Reconciliation Commission, 1998, <https://www.justice.gov.za/trc/report/index.htm>. The Commission, established in 1995 under the Promotion of National Unity and Reconciliation Act, took testimony from victims and perpetrators of apartheid-era violence as a public process of national reconciliation. The extent to which reconciliation was effective is disputed.

²¹ Trouillot describes a dialectic of mentions and silences, above, but does not invoke Hegel or frame the relationship between acts and narratives as dialectical. The Hegelian extension is my own.

history, not just acts of inscribing history, such that each is “raised” to a higher level and the process continues.²²

Where Silences Enter the Narrative

Silences can enter the narrative at various places. Trouillot identifies four “Moments” where silences enter historical production: “the moment of fact creation (the making of *sources*); the moment of fact assembly (the making of *archives*); the moment of fact retrieval (the making of *narratives*); and the moment of retrospective significance (the making of *history* in the final instance).”²³ Trouillot treats these as heuristic tools rather than rigid categories, using them as a general framework for understanding how silences enter the narrative. He also notes how they are not chronological. Sans Souci was a leader of the Haitian Revolution who was killed by Henry I; Henry I then named his royal palace Sans Souci, and over time the palace's fame silenced the memory of the man. In this case, the making of history in the final instance is in play, but Henry I does nothing to affect the sources, they remain.²⁴ Trouillot is specifically focused on how power, a political force, produces historical silences. And silences for Trouillot

²² The process Hegel calls *Aufhebung* and Derrida translates *la relève*, sometimes inadequately translated as “sublation” in English.

²³ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 26, 52, 57–59. For Trouillot, “the making of archives” is the organizing of sources. (52) The “making of history in the final instance” approximates what might otherwise be called canonization.

²⁴ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 27, 59.

are always active, transitive things, “one ‘silences’ a fact or an individual as a silencer silences a gun.”²⁵

Saidiya Hartman, a Black scholar of slavery and its afterlife whose work moves between history, literary criticism, and critical theory, identifies at least one further way in which silences enter the narrative, beyond the four moments identified above. Silences can be created by the inadequacy of theoretical frameworks themselves. The primary example of this is the way in which Black women’s labor is silenced because it exceeds the “conceptual categories [of even Black] critical lexicon.”²⁶ In other words, it is silenced through a failure to give it a name. A very similar idea of a “failure to name” is developed as a personal moral injury by Miranda Fricker. Her primary example is of women who were the victims of sexual harassment and assault, “[t]he ‘this’ they were going to break the silence about had no name.”²⁷ Fricker is focused on *epistemic* harms—harms to one’s capacity as a knower.²⁸ Whereas, I am focused on *ontological* effects, harms or otherwise, in that silences create historical persons—and *non-persons*—through narrative. By ‘ontological’ I mean having to do with being—with what and who exist as historical subjects—as opposed to what we know about them. Moreover, effects, including harms, can be both ontological and epistemic at the same time,²⁹ personal and general at the same time.

²⁵ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 48.

²⁶ Saidiya Hartman, “The Belly of the World: A Note on Black Women’s Labors,” *Souls* 18, no. 1 (2016): 167, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10999949.2016.1162596>.

²⁷ *Epistemic Injustice: Power and the Ethics of Knowing* (Oxford University Press, 2007), 150.

²⁸ *Epistemic Injustice*, 155 (emphasis original).

²⁹ See, e.g., Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 61, 113, 132 using both epistemological and ontological (production of persons) language.

Trouillot perhaps gestures at the failure to name when he says, “facts are never meaningless: indeed, they become facts only because they matter in some sense, *however minimal*.”³⁰ The problem here is in recognizing that they matter. While one might argue that a failure to name is an aspect of Trouillot’s moment of fact creation, it is distinct. If we don’t have a name for a fact, a category through which it can be understood, then it cannot assume a meaning. It cannot be judged to matter or not matter. In some sense, without a name it can’t even be meaningless. A fact for which there is no name is effectively a non-fact, for it never has the opportunity to be recognized as a source.

Trouillot’s Two Kinds of History

Trouillot critiques both positivism and constructivism—positivism holds that history can be objective and evidence-based; constructivism holds that history is always narrative construction. Positivism doesn’t leave room for consideration of why some things entered the historical narrative and some things did not.³¹ Constructivism, at its extreme end, can say that history is nothing but narrative, that events occurred if we say they did. He is particularly troubled by this latter argument, suggesting it would mean that it doesn’t matter whether millions died in the Holocaust, only whether the dominant narrative said they did.³²

Trouillot’s solution to this is to define two sides of historicity, “historicity 1” and “historicity 2”.³³ Historicity 1 is what actually happened, or the “materiality of the socio-

³⁰ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 29 (emphasis mine).

³¹ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 4–5.

³² Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 11–13.

³³ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 24, 29.

historical process”. Historicity 2 is historical narratives, or what is said to have happened.³⁴ The four moments of historical production discussed above operate entirely within historicity 2; historicity 1 is prior to all of them, the raw occurrence that, as Chapter 2 will argue, no source, archive, or narrative can fully recover. Power enters at the interface of these two sides of historicity. It trivializes certain history, certain memories, certain experiences, certain points of view, and excludes them from the historical narrative.³⁵

Through this process power asserts itself specifically as what Trouillot calls ‘archival power’. What is archived and how much importance it is given is determined through this archival power. It determines what is available for narration, the boundaries of historicity 2. It is also what determines who gets to write history.³⁶ Thus, the struggle for what is archived and how, is a struggle for historical power. While Trouillot acknowledges that developing new methods for uncovering and interpreting archival content is useful, focusing on this and ignoring how content enters, or is prohibited from entering, the archive, creates an “unnecessary restriction on the *battleground for historical power*”.³⁷ For instance, discovering more detailed records of enslavers may reveal further silences but does not, by itself, recover the voices of the enslaved—it concedes the battleground to the archive's own terms.

Trouillot sees the importance of historicity 2, and the difficulty if not impossibility, of getting any real sense of historicity 1. However, he holds the distinction firmly, concerned that

³⁴ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 106.

³⁵ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 115–116, Trouillot terms this the “Triviality Clause”. C.f. Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 9–39, describing an epistemological analog to the social contract through which acknowledgment of white supremacy is foreclosed.

³⁶ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 52.

³⁷ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 49 (emphasis mine).

without it, the question of what really happened becomes subordinate to who wins the battle for what is said to have happened. This is nowhere clearer than in his discussion of celebrations, which trivialize the historical process while mythicizing the narrative—a tension that suggests the distinction between the two may be harder to maintain than it first appears.³⁸

But what is the relationship between historicity 1 and historicity 2? Is it possible to know a historicity not inflected by power, historicity 1? Is this not the proper goal of history?

³⁸ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 118.

CHAPTER 2: THE ARCHIVE REPEATS

Trouillot describes the structure of historical narratives and how silences can be “made to speak”. But why doesn’t the archive foreclose other readings? Jacques Derrida, an Algerian-born French philosopher of Sephardic Jewish descent whose French citizenship was revoked under Vichy laws as a child, provides the first part of an answer: other readings can never be foreclosed. I will argue that power continuously attempts to foreclose meaning, and the content of the archive, but that its very attempt to do so ensures that foreclosure is impossible. I also argue that historicity 1, to the extent that it represents what actually occurred independent of its narration, is inaccessible.

I will suggest two analogies, each with its own inadequacies. First, historicity 1 is somewhat like a horizon; we know it is real, but no amount of technology will get you there. An inadequacy here is that this is not purely perspectival; it is not simply that historicity 1 recedes from us by its nature, though this may give some sense of it. It is also somewhat like a palimpsest, there are traces³⁹ of the text, but it is permanently and, at least as far as we can know, irrecoverably lost. However, we will see that this is inadequate as suggesting something that was once fully present, but the facts of history were gone the instant they arrived.⁴⁰

³⁹ “Trace” operates differently across the texts this thesis engages. Trouillot uses the term in a conventional historiographical sense, referring to artifacts and sources, without drawing on Derrida. Derrida’s trace is developed across his corpus; for the purposes of this thesis it is most consequential in *Archive Fever* and *Cinders*, and operative though not foregrounded in *Limited Inc*. It designates a structure in which reference occurs without an originary presence to ground it, not a material remainder but the mark of something that was never fully present. Throughout this chapter, “trace” follows the Derridean sense. This does not contradict the sense it is used by Trouillot but the Derridean trace exceeds the historiographical sense.

⁴⁰ This may also be true of the palimpsest but, but the nature of writing both complicates and defeats it, since a discussion of text as also subject to these structures, requires a full discussion of the structures.

I will start by discussing the basic sign in its iterability and citationality, then proceed to discuss the archive—as Derrida uses the term—which functions as both a component of and analog for historicity 2. I will end this chapter with a discussion of how the archive ultimately works against itself. I draw primarily on *Limited Inc* and *Archive Fever*, with *Cinders* appearing in Chapter 4. While Derrida does not expressly name white supremacy in these texts, his own history and his other works suggest the power he names in *Archive Fever* is informed by an understanding of white supremacy.

Iterability and Citation

The central insight of Derrida's account of language for this thesis is that no sign can ever have its context fully determined—meaning can never be foreclosed. He develops this through the concept of 'iterability'. It is a structure of language that any sign must be capable of being repeated, but not just repeated, repeated in a new context. A word wouldn't be a word if we couldn't use it again, differently. Derrida calls this structure "iterability". He constructs this term from *iter* (Latin, "again")—a cognate of Sanskrit इतर (itara, "other")—and *ability*. So, it is the ability to be both again and other.⁴¹ Of its nature, iteration must *always* alter; there is no pure repetition where a sign can be repeated without alteration.⁴² Iterability is a general structure, which calls for, but does not possess, a differential typology (*typologie différentielle*).⁴³

⁴¹ Jacques Derrida, "Signature Event Context," in *Limited Inc*, trans. Samuel Weber and Jeffrey Mehlman (Northwestern University Press, 2008), 7, 62.

⁴² Jacques Derrida, "Limited Inc a b c ...," in *Limited Inc*, trans. Samuel Weber (Northwestern University Press, 2008), 40.

⁴³ Jacques Derrida, "Signature événement contexte," in *Limited Inc* (Galilée, 1990), 45.

“Citation” is one type or modification (*modification déterminé*)⁴⁴ or mode (*détermination modalisante*)⁴⁵ of iterability. In *Sec*,⁴⁶ Derrida uses the language of species for the relationship of citation to iterability,⁴⁷ but he later complicates that by saying “[i]terability cannot be *simply* the genus, of which citation ... would be the species”.⁴⁸ However, iterability is not a transcendental condition of possibility of citation or its other modes.⁴⁹ This appears to be because iterability is self-corrupting and self-constituting, i.e. iterability itself has the ability to be iterated, or to be cited. And as Chapter 3 will show, this is exactly what happens in the domain of normative reiteration.

Derrida characterizes iterability as organizing its space “in a (as I often say) ‘quasi’-transcendental manner.”⁵⁰ Other types or modes of iterability exist, namely parasitism and example,⁵¹ perhaps also echo,⁵² though there appear to be indefinitely many others. Having called for a differential typology of them, Derrida later says this is impossible, at least insofar as

⁴⁴ Derrida, “Signature événement contexte,” 44.

⁴⁵ Jacques Derrida, “Limited Inc a b c ...,” in *Limited Inc* (Galilée, 1990), 186.

⁴⁶ Derrida’s abbreviation for “Signature événement contexte”, often styled “SEC” in English due to the difference in title case, but this obscures the French meaning “dry”, which Derrida makes use of in the text.

⁴⁷ Derrida, “Signature événement contexte,” 45. (“d’autres espèces d’itération à l’intérieur d’une itérabilité générale”), *espèces* was rendered as “kinds” by Weber and Mehlman, obscuring the nuance Derrida distinguishes in “Limited Inc a b c ...”.

⁴⁸ Derrida, “Limited Inc a b c ...,” trans. Weber, 100 (emphasis mine).

⁴⁹ Derrida, “Limited Inc a b c ...,” trans. Weber, 92, 100.

⁵⁰ Jacques Derrida, “Toward an Ethics of Discussion,” in *Limited Inc*, trans. Samuel Weber (Northwestern University Press, 2008), 127.

⁵¹ Derrida, “Limited Inc a b c ...,” trans. Weber, 89. Austin’s version of parasitism is the impetus for *Sec* and one of the key issues in Derrida’s argument with Austin and Searle.

⁵² Jacques Derrida, “A Certain Impossible Possibility of Saying the Event,” *Critical Inquiry* 33, no. 2 (2007): 3, <https://doi.org/10.1086/511506>.

it would limit iterability.⁵³ Iterability and its modes (e.g. citation) exceed the logic of classical taxonomy, citation entails iterability, which is its graphematic root; that is, citation always already involves iterability.⁵⁴

The mode of iterability known as ‘citation’ is of particular interest to this thesis. Citation is the ability for any sign to be cut off from its prior context, removed from its “original” meaning and “put between quotation marks” (figuratively, there is no need for literal quotation marks) in another place altogether. The quotation marks refer to its prior use, but they also signify that it has been removed from the prior context and placed in this new, radically different one, often for an altogether different purpose.⁵⁵

Additionally, we cannot fail to or choose not to exercise iterability or not cite. We cannot recreate the context of another.⁵⁶ To recreate their context would be to reinstantiate a past event, to repeat without iterating.⁵⁷ We *must* cite or use other modes of iterability in all of our communications.

To help illustrate ‘citation’ as Derrida is using this term, as a mode of iterability, consider the Fourteenth Amendment's equal protection clause. Written in 1868 to address the legal status of formerly enslaved people, the same words have been cited in contexts no drafter could have anticipated—corporate personhood, affirmative action, same-sex marriage. Each citation lifts the

⁵³ Derrida, “Limited Inc a b c ...,” trans. Weber, 99.

⁵⁴ Derrida, “Limited Inc a b c ...,” trans. Weber, 98. “Graphematic root” refers to properties of marks as such, citation is possible because marks must be minimally iterable to be marks. The root is *part of* that which grows from it, not merely its source or foundation.

⁵⁵ Derrida, “Signature Event Context,” 12.

⁵⁶ Derrida, “A Certain Impossible Possibility of Saying the Event,” 454.

⁵⁷ See discussion of the event in text accompanying note 84 below.

clause from its prior context and sets it down in a radically different one. The sign persists; the meaning is transformed. The drafters are powerless to prevent this, not because they are dead, but because the sign's iterability was always a condition of its functioning as a sign. Legal citation makes this structural feature of language visible, but citationality in Derrida's sense is not limited to formal citation—it is a condition of all signification.

Because all signs exhibit iterability, the capacity to be used in a different place differently, as a condition of being signs; and citationality, the capacity to be ripped from all prior context and placed in a new context (i.e. a sort of radical iterability), no context can confine a sign. This is true even for unknown signs, or ones for which the encoding has been lost. I can “cite” the paintings of Chauvet-Pont-d'Arc Cave or some ancient text in Linear A. It does not matter that I don't know what it “originally”, i.e. in its prior context, meant. I can use it creatively, I can use it as an example (as I did with the Fourteenth Amendment), I can use it in conversation with others about the prior meanings in which I propose interpretations, or I can re-encode it with a new meaning. All of these are equally available to me by virtue of the marks being signs. I cannot, however, remove it from all context, unless I can somehow use it as a non-sign.⁵⁸

So, the Fourteenth Amendment, in its existence as text, as sign, with its adherent ability to be used again in different ways, is its iterability. That I can rip the text from all prior contexts and set it down in a new one—in this case, as an exemplar of its own citationality—is its citationality. A mode of iterability that is perhaps more radical than merely using it again

⁵⁸ Whether that is possible to remove something from its status as a sign is irrelevant to and beyond the scope of this paper. Perhaps if I were to use it to physically prop something up in such a way that it was itself not identifiable; but even this may be just another context.

differently. And from this it follows that no text can ever have its context foreclosed. It can never have its context, its meaning, fully saturated. For if it could, I could no longer cite it—it would no longer be capable of being used again, differently—and would have ceased to be a sign.

While Derrida does not say as much in *Sec* or “Limited Inc a b c ...”, iterability and citation necessarily assume an outside to the context of the sign. A sign may be used again in a *different* way, one which has not been used in prior contexts. This is not the same as saying that there is an outside *of* context in any absolute sense—“Nothing *exists* outside context”.⁵⁹ But any particular context has a relative outside, i.e. other contexts into which it could be inserted. This will be important in the discussion of the archive.

The Archive

To articulate what is past does not mean to recognize “how it really was.” It means to take control of a memory, as it flashes in a moment of danger.
—Walter Benjamin (Thesis VI)⁶⁰

In *Archive Fever*, Derrida is expressly political, acknowledging that power structures the entire work: “there is no political power without control of the archive”.⁶¹ The archive derives from Ancient Greek words for one who commands, the *archon*, and his house, the *arkheion*, as well as the word for the beginning or commencement.⁶² The *archon*, is responsible for those

⁵⁹ Derrida, “Toward an Ethics of Discussion,” 136, 152 (emphasis original). Here, Derrida is commenting here on the misunderstandings surrounding his famous phrase *il n’y a pas de hors-texte*. Cf. Derrida, *Positions*, 64: “I am not even sure that there can be a ‘concept’ of an absolute exterior.”

⁶⁰ Walter Benjamin, “On the Concept of History,” Marxists.Org, accessed March 18, 2026, <https://www.marxists.org/reference/archive/benjamin/1940/history.htm>.

⁶¹ Jacques Derrida, *Archive Fever: A Freudian Impression* (University of Chicago Press, 1996), 4n1.

⁶² Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 1–2.

things deposited with him (“consigned” to him). He protects them and thereby decides what is allowed to be a part of them. In doing so, he both exercises power over the archive and has power by virtue of this exercise.⁶³ His is a place of privilege, the place of gathering together of signs (another meaning of “consign”) and it gives him the authority to be the author of history.⁶⁴

The silencing of the Haitian Revolution operated on two levels. At one level, it was suppression—both in the common sense of the word and in the sense used by Freud—deliberate, material, the conscious exercise of colonial power to control the narrative.⁶⁵ Trouillot captures this precisely, “one ‘silences’ a fact or an individual as a silencer silences a gun.”⁶⁶ But at another level, the revolution was *unthinkable*—it exceeded the conceptual categories available to European thought.⁶⁷ This is repression in the Freudian sense Derrida invokes: a foreclosure prior to conscious thought. Had Europeans recognized the revolution as unthinkable, it would already have entered the domain of the thinkable. The two operations are not alternatives; the material suppression was reinforced by, and in part depended on, the conceptual foreclosure.

Two Competing Drives

The archive depends on a process of ‘consignation’, by which Derrida means both a process of entrusting into someone’s care (the common English meaning of “consign”) and to

⁶³ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 1–2.

⁶⁴ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 3.

⁶⁵ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 27–28, 77–78.

⁶⁶ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 48. Interestingly, silencers for guns are more correctly called “suppressors”, re-emphasizing this connection in the transitive use of “to silence”

⁶⁷ Trouillot, *Silencing the Past*, 82, 85.

gather together signs into a collection, from the Latin meaning “to write down, to record”.⁶⁸ This also demands a process of repetition.⁶⁹ Here, Derrida adopts Freud’s psychoanalytic term “repetition” as in “repetition compulsion”, a term which is intertwined with Freud’s “death drive”.⁷⁰ Again, this is a demonstration of iterability and citation. The word, in the context of Austin and “simpl[e] repetition”, was one he expressly distinguished from iterability in *Sec* and “Limited Inc, a b c ...”.⁷¹ But here, in the context of Freud and the archive, he uses it freely as yet another mode of iterability.

The death drive, or repetition compulsion, is necessary to making the archive. The archon must continue to write down the archive, to repeat it, for if no one can hear or read it, it is not an archive. An archive that never records, repeats, an event, is no archive at all.⁷² But the archon also wants the archive to remain unchanged. This is the “conservation drive”.⁷³ Derrida calls the conservation drive, the *archive drive*, as it is the drive to keep things in the archive safe forever. It is Freud’s Eros or “life drive”.⁷⁴ The death drive, destruction drive, or aggression drive,⁷⁵ Derrida calls the *anarchivic* or *archiviolithic drive*, acts through repetition and changing (adding

⁶⁸ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 3, 11.

⁶⁹ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 11.

⁷⁰ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 11–12. See Freud, *The Ego and the Id*.

⁷¹ See, e.g., Derrida, “Toward an Ethics of Discussion,” 129.

⁷² Even merely *reading* the archive is a form of iterability. The reader receives the text in a different context from that in which it was set down.

⁷³ The death drive is itself ‘conservative’ in Freud’s sense—a drive to return to a prior state—but Derrida’s ‘conservation drive’ refers specifically to the Eros pole of the post-1920 dualism, the drive to preserve and accumulate. Derrida is aware of this entanglement, the archive always works against itself, but maintains the distinction for analytical purposes.

⁷⁴ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 19, 12. See Freud, *Beyond the Pleasure Principle*.

⁷⁵ All names that Derrida cites to Freud. *Archive Fever*, 10.

to and reinterpreting) the archive, the archive as a perfect record of the past is destroyed.⁷⁶ But at the same time, without the drive to destroy the archive, there is no possibility of the archive. This contradiction in the death drive, how it both acts against the archive drive and makes it possible, is *le mal d'archive*, usually translated as “the archive fever” it is a fever in the sense of an illness or a madness, in this case a self-destructive and inescapable drive.⁷⁷ Citing Freud, Derrida describes how the death drive in its anarchiving destruction both produces the archive and reduces it, “on occasion to ashes, and beyond”.⁷⁸

While Derrida doesn't say it explicitly, it's implied, via Freud, that we all have a drive to archive, whether it's as an official archon or as the archivist of our own memories. We are driven to preserve the past, which requires both recording it and not changing it, two incompatible drives, since every time we record, we also change—at the very least we change something about the context. In other words, we want to record the past perfectly, something iterability has shown us to be impossible.

In the “Postscript” to *Archive Fever*, Derrida goes into detail about Freud's analysis of a novel by Wilhelm Jensen.⁷⁹ The novel is about a certain archeologist, Hanold. Hanold has a bas-relief of a young Roman woman who is walking and whom he names “Gradiva” (after *Mars*

⁷⁶ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 10.

⁷⁷ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 12.

⁷⁸ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 94. Citing Sigmund Freud, *Beyond the Pleasure Principle*. The resonance with Derrida's *Cinders*, discussed in Chapter 4, is deliberate.

⁷⁹ The novel is *Gradiva: Ein pompejanisches Phantasiestück* by Wilhelm Jensen (1903), the subject of Sigmund Freud, *Der Wahn und die Träume in W. Jensens „Gradiva”* (Franz Deuticke, 1908).

Gradivus, “Gradivus” an eponym for the god Mars, means “one who steps forth”)⁸⁰ and whom he fancies is from Pompeii.⁸¹ He wants a sort of “pure” repetition, an artifact, in this case an impression of her foot in the ash of Vesuvius, that is better than anything other archeologists have achieved. An artifact that is almost identical to the actual impression before the foot was raised.⁸² But at the very moment of impression, the iterability of the impression was already a part of it; it was always already that which was iterable. More than this is implied, every iteration is itself always already iterable, divided in advance, always with one foot in the future. There is no perfect archival specimen, there is not even the imperfect specimen we seek because that is the singularity, the condition of uniqueness, and even the trace is not unique to itself, “not even a past present”. We cannot find the original; we cannot find the trace in the literal sense, the one we look for was never there.⁸³ This is not to say that no one was ever there, but all of our understanding of Gradiva, comes from citations of traces. The uniterated, the uncited, the “original” was never fully present and accessible to us, even at the moment of its origin. This is the condition of the event as such. Events are unique and unrepeatable, yet any attempt to say the event presupposes its iterability—that it can be said again, differently. The event is always already iterable, which works to erase it from the outset.⁸⁴

⁸⁰ *A Latin Dictionary*, Founded on Andrews’ edition of Freund’s Latin dictionary, ed. Charlton T. Lewis and Charles Short (Clarendon Press, 1879), under “Gradivus.”

⁸¹ Wilhelm Jensen, *Gradiva: Ein pompejanisches Phantasiestück* (Carl Reissner Verlag, 1903), 4.

⁸² Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 97–98.

⁸³ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 98–100.

⁸⁴ Derrida, “A Certain Impossible Possibility of Saying the Event,” 452, 453.

At the very end of *Archive Fever*, Derrida talks about secrets that Freud, or others, have kept and have concealed from everyone, taking them to their grave. Here we are particularly talking about secret thoughts and feelings, things that, unless recorded somewhere, have no discernible trace. Secrets that may have burned without any remains, “without a name, ... and without even an ash”.⁸⁵ This seems to suggest that some silences are gone forever. The archive simultaneously preserves and effaces, in effect, it mentions and it silences. But what is mentioned and what is silenced are both inaccessible except in their iterability. Does the silence have iterability?

Earlier in the text he gives us some clues. Yosef Hayim Yerushalmi was a scholar of Jewish history. *Archive Fever* engages at length with Yerushalmi’s book *Freud’s Moses*, particularly its extraordinary concluding “Monologue with Freud”—a direct address to Freud’s ghost, which Derrida reads as an archival act that demonstrates the archive’s constitutive orientation toward a future that may never arrive. Derrida says, speaking of Yerushalmi’s letter to Freud’s ghost, “[t]here is no meta-archive”.⁸⁶ There is no meta-archive because any commentary on the archive inscribes itself into the archive.⁸⁷ *Freud’s Moses* is engaging with Freud’s work *Moses and Monotheism*, a text in which Freud reconstructs Moses as an Egyptian nobleman, a speculative historiographic act that itself becomes part of the archive it comments on.⁸⁸ Derrida calls *Moses and Monotheism*, “Freud’s ‘historical novel’”. The quotation marks

⁸⁵ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 101.

⁸⁶ Echoing Lacan’s ‘there is no meta-language’.

⁸⁷ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 67.

⁸⁸ Sigmund Freud, *Moses and Monotheism*, trans. Katherine Jones (Hogarth Press and the Institute of Psycho-Analysis, 1939; originally published as *Der Mann Moses Und Die Monotheistische Religion*), 29. Notably,

around ‘historical novel’ are significant: Freud’s own description of his work is *cited* to show how even self-commentary on the archive becomes archival. Moreover, “the archive is never closed. It opens out of the future.”⁸⁹ Every attempt at meta-archive expands the archive. This is a statement of the archive’s citationality. The archive cannot constrain its own future interpretability. It is always already corrupted by its own future iterability, by future citations of it.

The archive wants to constrain, to conserve, its own context, but it can only repeat the archival act of gathering meanings together. Every commentary on the archive will either be excluded from the archive or incorporated into it as the archive creates itself. And we can comment on silences, iterating them. A silence, even one that appears absolute, is iterable and archivable as commentary on the silence in the archive. In the same way that there is no perfect preservation, there can be no perfect destruction. But in both cases what remains is not “literal”, it’s a trace subject to further interpretation.

this is also a “haunting”. As described by Freud, Moses transmitted his Akhenaten religion to the Hebrews, who later murdered Moses and then repressed the murder, which haunts Abrahamic faiths. 138–143.

⁸⁹ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 68.

CHAPTER 3: TOPOLOGIES OF POWER

With respect to the archive, Derrida gestures at the necessity of that which is not within the archive being necessary to the archive. That is the future of interpretation it is open to. Likewise, in *Sec*, the new and unlimitable contexts are the outside. In *Disseminations*, Derrida was a bit more explicit about the necessity of the outside to the understanding of the inside when he says that memory both requires an outside to which it is in relation and it is constantly invaded by that outside.⁹⁰ Both of these aspects, constitution and invasion, will be important in their turn.

Judith Butler is a queer philosopher and gender theorist whose work examines how regulatory norms produce the very categories, such as sex and gender, that they purport to describe. Butler takes up this topology of an inside and outside to explain how categories of sex and gender are naturalized, showing that sex itself is a product of the regulatory norms it purports to ground. This invasion of the outside, that is a part of iterability itself, is necessarily where definitions of the body, and historicity, are always already changing and it is therefore, the “front line” of Trouillot’s battleground for historical power. Furthermore, the authorizing norms of gender, or of history, will never *allow* this change and only historical methods that transgress the authorizing norms can do the work of unsilencing.

I draw primarily on Butler’s *Bodies That Matter* in this chapter, which proceeds in two movements: first, “The Inside Must Have an Outside”, introduces the constitutive outside, a concept Butler derives indirectly from Derrida; then “Power Must Repeat Itself” applies the constitutive outside and iterability to history and the archive. Butler’s analysis works through

⁹⁰ Jacques Derrida, *Dissemination*, trans. Barbara Johnson (University of Chicago Press, 1981), 109.

racialized bodies as well as gendered ones, and I take up the racial dimension of the constitutive outside in the discussion of empire and barbarian below.

The Inside Must Have an Outside

We can schematize the way in which things are constituted for Derrida as “X is constituted by non-X”, and we can call non-X the “constitutive outside”.⁹¹ There is also a movement from non-X to X (and from X to non-X) through iterability, the actions of the archive, etc. One might think that this sounds like Hegelian negation; it is beyond the scope of this paper to distinguish Derrida’s project from Hegel’s; however, we can note in passing that Derrida critiques the Hegelian dialectic’s process of *Aufhebung* for its sense of “raising up” and its attempt to always conserve meaning and move towards a synthesis. The struggle between X and non-X, which is the struggle for meaning, is never resolvable, there is always an irreconcilable remainder.⁹²

Judith Butler takes up what is likely another mode of iterability, *reiteration*, a term they use to describe the particular performative repetition that authorizing norms require and that causes the naturalization of concepts of gender and sexuality. As something is cited repeatedly, it reinscribes the boundary between the inside and the outside and creates an impression that it was always so, even as it necessarily continues to change. Butler, engaging with Irigaray and Lacan,

⁹¹ Henry Staten, *Wittgenstein and Derrida* (University of Nebraska Press, 1986), 16–17. Butler’s use of the constitutive outside operates by the same logic as the trace, however, Butler does not thematize the trace in *Bodies That Matter*. See the discussion of the trace in Chapter 2 at note 39.

⁹² Jacques Derrida, “Différance,” in *Margins of Philosophy*, trans. Alan Bass (Harvester Wheatsheaf, 1982), 19–21, 19n23; Staten, *Wittgenstein and Derrida*, 17n22. The phrasing “irreconcilable remainder” is my own, but cf. Derrida’s “*reste, irréductible à la force dominante*” in *Sec 55* (Galilée) emphasis original. The formulation echoes Schelling’s ‘irreducible remainder,’ though I do not develop that connection here. I prefer ‘irreconcilable’ to emphasize that the remainder cannot be reconciled with the inside, not merely that it cannot be reduced.

shows the necessity of the female body⁹³ as “constitutive outside” of the male body. That is, what is male is defined by what is not-male, i.e. female. This is the first movement of a double movement and produces the constitutive outside; the second, discussed below, is the continuous reiteration that enforces and reinscribes the boundary. Outside of male is a “zone of uninhabitability”, which is unintelligible to it, “unthinkable”, even.⁹⁴ Outside the female is doubly so. This zone of uninhabitability is the domain of the unsayable, as distinguished from the merely unsaid in Chapter 1. The unsaid could be mentioned but is not; the unsayable is what the authorizing norms have rendered unintelligible—it cannot enter the domain of history because the norms cannot recognize it. The foreclosure that produces this outside is an action of power, which marks out a “domain” in which its “regulatory law” enforces gender’s performance according to the norms it has established—the archival drive in Derrida’s sense.⁹⁵

Like all inscriptions, the inscription of the gendered body has a topology. It may help to analogize this topology to an empire. The empire has a border outside of which are not just foreigners (literally “the outsiders”),⁹⁶ but also the barbarians, a word recorded in antiquity to mean unintelligible people, babblers (“I suppose that the word barbarian was at first uttered onomatopoeically in reference to people who enunciated words only with difficulty and talked

⁹³ For simplicity, as this is a paper on history, not gender, I will use “female body” “feminine” and “woman”, and related terms, roughly synonymously, in line with Butler, as well the corresponding “male body”, “masculine”, and “man”. Likewise, I will not distinguish between sex and gender. I acknowledge that all such distinctions are going through their own processes of iterability and their equivalence may be in question.

⁹⁴ Judith Butler, *Bodies That Matter: On the Discursive Limits of “Sex”* (Routledge, 2011), x, xii–xxx, 13, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203828274>.

⁹⁵ See note 74.

⁹⁶ “foreign, adj., n.², & adv.,” *OED Online* (Oxford University Press), accessed April 3, 2026, https://www.oed.com/dictionary/foreign_adj.

harshly and raucously”)⁹⁷ Strabo notes semantic drift from an original onomatopoeic use as an insult for those who spoke unintelligibly and later developing into an ethnic category meaning “non-Greeks”.⁹⁸ Notably, even foreigner is spatial before it’s social.⁹⁹ This is significant because it shows the performative inscription Butler describes, along with the effect of reiteration. The phrase meaning “those whom I can’t understand” inscribes a zone of uninhabitability which through reiteration (essentially calling people names) inscribes a normative category of those who are not one of us. Their lives are quite unintelligible to the empire and they do not *matter*.¹⁰⁰

The semantic drift also shows that the constitutive outside operates through racialization, not only through gender/sex. Butler knows this; they engage directly with the intersection of racialized and gendered bodies in their chapters “Gender is Burning” and “Passing, Queering”. Just as the barbarian-as-unintelligible is racially constructed, the empire’s inside is constituted as a white inside. In order to maintain this, the empire must perform racialization repetitively, because the boundary cannot be fixed.

But it is that area beyond the borders of the empire by which we define the empire. The empire has no identity without a not-us to construct itself against, to inscribe its borders within. So, the outside, which is unintelligible, unthinkable, is necessary to the constitution of the inside.

⁹⁷ Strabo, *Geography*, vol. 6, trans. H. L. Jones, Loeb Classical Library 223 (Harvard University Press, 1929), 14.2.28. Greek text (Meineke): οἶμαι δὲ τὸ βάρβαρον κατ’ ἀρχὰς ἐκπεφωνῆσθαι οὕτως κατ’ ὀνοματοποιίαν ἐπὶ τῶν δυσεκφόρως καὶ σκληρῶς καὶ τραχέως λαλοῦντων. The word βάρβαρον is cognate with the Sanskrit word बर्बर, “barbara”, meaning both “non-Aryan” and “idiot”.

⁹⁸ Strabo, *Geography*, vol. 6, 14.2.28. Greek text (Meineke): ἐκείνους οὖν ἰδίως ἐκάλεσαν βαρβάρους, ἐν ἀρχαῖς μὲν κατὰ τὸ λοιδορον, ὡς ἂν παχυστόμους ἢ τραχυστόμους, εἶτα κατεχρησάμεθα ὡς ἐθνικῶ κοινῷ ὀνόματι ἀντιδιαροῦντες πρὸς τοὺς Ἕλληνας.

⁹⁹ *OED Online*, “foreign, adj., n.², & adv.”

¹⁰⁰ Butler, *Bodies That Matter*, x.

This is what is meant by the outside is ‘inside’ the subject as its own founding repudiation, or that the outside “haunts” the inside.¹⁰¹ The definition of the empire includes within it the unthinkable barbarian.

Power Must Repeat Itself

This haunting creates an anxiety that is behind the continuous repetition, suggesting that the repetition drive is directly tied to this haunting.¹⁰² The Archon knows that the future is a threat to the conservation of the archive and thus repeats it furiously to reinscribe its consigned content. Likewise, male must include female, its founding repudiation, within it. The archive, being open to the future, includes that which is not consigned to the archive, within it. And historical narrative (historicity 2) must include that which is not allowed within the narrative. Narratives of Black, Indigenous, and queer lives are here, though they are not self-identical with “Black History”, “Indigenous History”, “Queer History”, which are themselves products of the authorizing norms.

Power wants to inscribe the boundary between the inside and the outside once and for all, but this is impossible. In much the same way that as the archon must archive through the repetition drive, authorizing norms require the performance of gender according to those norms, i.e. heterosexual norms. This is the second half of the double movement that was begun as the

¹⁰¹ E.g., Butler, *Bodies That Matter*, x, 26–27. “Haunt” is a “citation” to Derrida.

¹⁰² Butler, *Bodies That Matter*, 181. The anxiety Butler identifies here appears to be structurally resonant with Heidegger’s *Angst* (*Being and Time*, §40), both are objectless (there is no determinate threat), both disclose a structural insufficiency (for Heidegger, ontological groundlessness; for Butler, an impossibility of resolution), both produce a compulsive response (Butler’s repetition, Heidegger’s fleeing). Functionally, they diverge: Butler’s anxiety has no *telos* analogous to Heidegger’s “being-toward-death”, differing loci (compare Anxiety as the Anxiety of Dasein with anxiety as structural to power within a discursive-political field), and Butler’s creates a political opening for resistance that is completely absent from Heidegger’s authenticity.

production of the constitutive outside above; it enforces a performance of masculinity that is in accord with and reiterates the circumscribing norms.¹⁰³ Because “pure repetition” is impossible, i.e. iterability is inescapable, the performance is never the same. In enforcing the boundary, the empire must constantly redraw the boundary on an ever-changing landscape and an ever-changing people.

Therefore, power has two contradictions it must simultaneously deal with. The unintelligible outside is already inside, haunting the identity of the inside. Iterability’s modes—citation, performativity, (archival) repetition, normative reiteration, and so on—will always result in *différance*:¹⁰⁴ an irreconcilable remainder, an identity that is not identical. The question that remains is what practice becomes possible, and defensible, within this instability.

¹⁰³ See, e.g., Butler, *Bodies That Matter*, xii–xxx, 59–60, 70, 140.

¹⁰⁴ Derrida, “Différance.” *Différance* is Derrida's neologism, coined in his 1968 essay by the same name, designating the movement by which meaning is simultaneously differed (deferred in time) and differed (differentiated from other meanings), such that no sign ever achieves full presence or self-identity. The term is untranslatable and is spelled with an *a* rather than an *e* to mark a distinction inaudible in spoken French.

CHAPTER 4: CITING SILENCES

Are we not touched by the same breath of air which was among that which came before?
is there not an echo of those who have been silenced in the voices to which we lend our
ears today?

—Walter Benjamin (Thesis II)¹⁰⁵

Saidiya Hartman, introduced briefly in Chapter 1, is a scholar of slavery and its afterlives, working at the intersection of history, literary studies, and Black feminist theory. She is a professor of English at Columbia University, working on the archive of Atlantic slavery. Her work wrestles with silences, often the extreme silences of slave ships where the only records are of the commodification of humans. Her practice of “critical fabulation” and the grammar it requires is the focus of this chapter, which proceeds in four movements: first, “Hartman and Venus” introduces an extreme silencing, absolute but for a sole entry in a court record; second, “Cinders and Ash” returns to Derrida for the idea that silences themselves may be cited in the archive and that our responsibility is to those silences; third, “Does History Speak in the Subjunctive Mood?” explores the grammar of critical fabulation and how speaking of silences stretches to the limits of language, and it introduces my concept of the hauntological irrealis to name what Hartman is reaching for; finally “The Hauntology in Hartman” explains why Hartman, in using the “least wrong” grammar, successfully cites the silences.

Hartman and Venus

In “Venus in Two Acts”, Hartman confronts what may be the hardest problem in the study of historical silences: a girl who existed, who suffered, who died, and of whom almost

¹⁰⁵ Benjamin, “On the Concept of History.”

nothing remains.¹⁰⁶ Venus is one of several figures Hartman engages in this essay, but she is Hartman's most sustained focus and the figure through whom Hartman articulates the constitutive limits of the white-supremacist archive. Venus was a young enslaved African girl held on the slave ship *Recovery*, captained by John Kimber, during the late eighteenth-century transatlantic slave trade. She died on the voyage, having been subjected to violence whose specifics the archive registers only obliquely. The only reason there is a record at all is that Captain John Kimber was tried for the murder of another girl. Venus appears in the archive only as a name spoken during the trial—not as a witness, not as a subject, but as a legal instrument in a case that was ultimately decided in the captain's favor.¹⁰⁷ As Hartman writes, Venus “‘never will have any existence outside the precarious domicile of words’ that allowed her to be murdered.”¹⁰⁸ The archive did not merely fail to record her; it recorded her death in a form that served her killers and then fell silent. Not even her name was her own. Venus was the name given to her by the crew.¹⁰⁹ What remains is not a gap waiting to be filled but a structured absence, the shape of a violence. Leaving this absence as irrecoverable reinscribes the silence. Filling the silence does further violence by creating a fiction.

In Trouillot's terms, Venus's situation is overdetermined. The silence entered at the moment of fact creation; the archive produced her only as a legal instrument in a case. The silence entered at the moment of fact assembly; the court determined in what ways she would be

¹⁰⁶ Saidiya Hartman, “Venus in Two Acts,” *Small Axe: A Caribbean Journal of Criticism* 12, no. 2 (2008): 7–14, <https://doi.org/10.1215/-12-2-1>.

¹⁰⁷ Hartman, “Venus in Two Acts,” 7.

¹⁰⁸ Saidiya V. Hartman, *Lose Your Mother: A Journey along the Atlantic Slave Route*, 1st ed (Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2007), 137. Cited in Hartman, “Venus in Two Acts,” 9.

¹⁰⁹ Hartman, *Lose Your Mother*, 141.

legible and foreclosed others. For the moment of narrative retrieval, this is silence itself; there is nothing to retrieve. The silence entered at the moment of retrospective significance; the verdict in favor of her murderer was established as the only historical record. Each silence compounds the others and magnifies the violence. Approaching Venus's situation from inside history's authorizing norms is futile. Approaching it from outside, as Hartman does, risks the judgment of archival power decreeing the work is fiction. This makes critical fabulation indispensable as a practice of unsettling boundary work, exploiting the archive's need to continuously define itself against its outside.

Hartman's response to this condition is the subject of this chapter. She calls her method "critical fabulation",¹¹⁰ a practice that neither fills the silence with fiction nor accepts the archive's violence as final. Understanding what this method is doing—philosophically, grammatically, and hauntologically¹¹¹—requires a detour through the theoretical structure of what traces¹¹² remain when the archive has done its worst. I will return to Hartman and to Venus after that detour, better equipped to say what kind of speech critical fabulation is, and why it is the least wrong speech available.

¹¹⁰ Hartman, "Venus in Two Acts," 11.

¹¹¹ Derrida coined *hantologie* (translated "hauntology") in *Specters of Marx* as a near-homophone of *ontologie* in French, where the initial *h* is silent; the term is meant to suggest a register that is neither presence nor absence, a mode of being that is constitutively spectral. Jacques Derrida, *Specters of Marx: The State of the Debt, the Work of Mourning and the New International*, trans. Peggy Kamuf (Routledge, 2012), 202.

¹¹² See note 39 in Chapter 2 for a discussion of how 'trace' operates across the texts this thesis engages.

*Cinders and Ash*¹¹³

[N]othing which has ever happened is to be given as lost to history. ... Each of its lived moments becomes a citation *a l'ordre du jour*.
—Walter Benjamin (Thesis III)¹¹⁴

The structure that Hartman confronts, traces so attenuated they barely register as traces at all, is what Derrida theorizes in *Cinders*. How gone are the traces of those who have gone? We want to think they are found in remnants of artifacts, that we will find evidence of a story that is misunderstood or overlooked. But while we may put our efforts on trying to revive voices hidden in the archive, those are not the voices we are longing for. There is no evidence or artifact that will tell us why Albert Cashier enlisted in the Union Army as a man. There is no lost page that will tell us how Anne Frank felt on the Fourth of August. At the end of *Archive Fever*, Derrida suggests that these are lost forever, without even ash, secrets that remained within the minds of people and went with them to their graves. The silences Trouillot describes are absences that promise a completion that will never arrive. But many other traces are with us, and it is to these that we must attend.

Some time before *Archive Fever*, Derrida said that “the best paradigm for traces, ..., is not, ...the trail of the hunt, the furrow in the sand, the wake in the sea, love of the step for its imprint”, these leave too much of themselves.¹¹⁵ He is interested rather in the extreme case, the trace that has destroyed itself, the trace that has exceeded the limits of language to even describe. He is thinking of the Holocaust, but here also is the victim of the Transatlantic slave trade, often

¹¹³ The French *cendres* encompasses both 'cinders' and 'ash'; see also note 78 in Chapter 2.

¹¹⁴ Benjamin, “On the Concept of History.”

¹¹⁵ Jacques Derrida, *Cinders*, trans. Ned Lukacher (University of Nebraska Press, 1991), 43.

left as the barest impression that they were there at all. Here is the cinder of the 19th century possibly queer person, who didn't ever express their identity in words. The cinder of the Indigenous person killed by smallpox. And the traces aren't always to be found in the record, Hartman's phrase "the afterlife of slavery"¹¹⁶ captures a very visible trace of the past that is here *in* the present, though not itself present, it haunts the present.

Derrida gestures at an ethic of handling these traces and how we speak of them in *Cinders*, but also that it is an unsolvable problem. We must make an interpretation, and by "must" I mean that the very act of contemplating a trace results in an interpretation that we cannot avoid, and which is always, by the laws of iterability, one possibility among many.¹¹⁷ Here, Derrida expressly applies this even to silences,

[U]ne interprétation, une seule parmi d'autres. A chaque syllabe, à *chaque silence même*, une décision s'est imposée : elle ne fut pas toujours délibérée, ni parfois la même d'une répétition à l'autre.

Here's an interpretation, one among others. At each syllable, *even at each silence*, a decision is imposed: it was not always deliberate, nor sometimes even the same from one repetition to the other.¹¹⁸

Something is also owed to the fire, some kind of debt to the past,¹¹⁹ but also in some way, the cinder is a gift or "in place of the gift", it cannot be repaid, both because the cinder points to a past that isn't available to us, that has been destroyed, and because by its unreadability, it means we can't really know what we owe or to whom. Were these conditions otherwise—were the past recoverable or the cinder readable—it would become transactional, and that is not a

¹¹⁶ Hartman, *Lose Your Mother*, 6.

¹¹⁷ Derrida, *Cinders*, 25.

¹¹⁸ Derrida, *Cinders*, 25 (printed in parallel French/English text) (emphasis mine).

¹¹⁹ Derrida, *Cinders*, 39.

proper relation to the past. The obligation is existential, and hauntological. Hauntology is Derrida's term for what is neither present nor absent but returns as the outside returning to the constitutive inside, unsettling the inside.¹²⁰ It is this hauntological condition—the trace that is neither recoverable nor fully lost—that critical fabulation inhabits, and that the hauntological irrealis, developed below, attempts to name grammatically. The trace exists because the fire of history has always already consumed it. The fire must be acknowledged. We must recognize that it gives us a “cinder signal” that “something or someone of whom [the fire] will say nothing but this rough sketch” but then that also must vanish into flame. “That is what is owed to the fire.”¹²¹

When Christina Sharpe speaks of the “wake”, she is not suggesting there is still a *physical* trace in the water, evidence of a ship that has passed carrying men, women, and children, let alone that this will somehow tell us how they felt or what they thought.¹²² Rather she is calling our attention to a trace that is present *in our society* and in the structure of that society. The wake, the hold, are the structural, and often very concrete, present violence against Black people. The wake *is* the afterlife of slavery. These are traces of hidden stories that have a palpable effect in the present. Black life within a white dominated society *as* citation of the Transatlantic slave trade and the commodification of people.

So far, we have spoken of these traces in rather obscure language. How can we do so more openly, in a way that actively transgresses the authorizing norms of historicity, without

¹²⁰ Derrida, *Specters of Marx*, 199, 202. “Constitutive outside”, as discussed in Chapter 3, is not Derrida's formulation but Staten's.

¹²¹ Derrida, *Cinders*, 36–37. Notably at 202, Derrida ties this back to iterability, though without expressly referencing *Sec*.

¹²² Christina Sharpe, *In the Wake: On Blackness and Being* (Duke University Press, 2016). Sharpe does suggest that *something* is there but the metaphysics of that and its differentiation from Derrida's trace is beyond the scope of this thesis.

suggesting that we know things that we do not, and without devolving into something that is no longer tied to any past, pure speculative fiction?

Does History Speak in the Subjunctive Mood?

Towards the end of “Venus in Two Acts”, Saidiya Hartman asks “Is it possible to exceed or negotiate the constitutive limits of the archive? By advancing a series of speculative arguments and exploiting the capacities of the subjunctive (a grammatical mood that expresses doubts, wishes, and possibilities), in fashioning a narrative, which is based upon archival research...”¹²³ English has largely traded off technically subjunctive morphology for a modal system¹²⁴, so I read this as a call to work carefully and deliberately in precise grammatical registers that de-position the speaker’s epistemic state. This reading is based on her then using the English future perfect (negated), “never will have any existence”¹²⁵ and the conditional perfect, “what could have been”, “if I could have conjured ...it might have been possible...that could have blossomed... Venus could have beheld ...”¹²⁶ This is not imprecision by any means, it’s Hartman constructing periphrastically what would be a subjunctive in, say, a Spanish

¹²³ Hartman, “Venus in Two Acts,” 11.

¹²⁴ F. R. Palmer, *Mood and Modality*, 2nd ed, Cambridge Textbooks in Linguistics (Cambridge University Press, 2001), 4.

¹²⁵ Hartman, “Venus in Two Acts,” 9. “Will have” followed by a noun is not standard future perfect morphology; rather, it’s standard simple future morphology. However, an ordinary simple future using “have” would indicate mere future possession, e.g. “will have candy”. English’s relatively analytic structure reveals what Hartman’s use of “will have” is doing: particularly in “never will have” rather than “will never have”, and followed by the abstract nominal complement “any existence”, it semantically approximates “never will have been” or “never will have existed” without being grammatically identical to either. This is creating a future perfect-like aspect periphrastically.

¹²⁶ Hartman, “Venus in Two Acts,” 8, 11.

subordinate clause, where English has no such morphology. And it is an attempt to push the limits of English and of language more generally.

The broader grammatical category within which the subjunctive operates, linguists call the *irrealis*, which marks propositions as non-actualized. Palmer describes this as distinct from the *realis*, which marks propositions as having actually occurred or occurring, generally corresponding to the indicative. The subjunctive is the morphological instantiation of the *irrealis* in Indo-European languages; the English modal system is largely the subjunctive's periphrastic replacement.¹²⁷ What I argue in this chapter is that Hartman is reaching toward something beyond the *irrealis* as linguists understand it, to a mode we might call the 'hauntological *irrealis*', in which the non-actualized is not merely hypothetical or wished for, but ontologically foreclosed by the archival structures that produced the trace. The fire burned what was there to ash and beyond, the content is irrecoverable, but "Cinders there are: Place there is".¹²⁸ This is not a grammatical category. It is the name for what language can approach but cannot reach.

While English can often get awkward here, even other European languages with more robust mood systems, like Spanish, are limited. In some cases this can result in complicated or grammatically incorrect constructions in English, while in other cases it allows English to expose what Spanish or Latin obscures in morphology by doing with modal auxiliary verbs what Spanish does in a single inflected form. It is uncertain whether any language offers a genuinely non-subject-centered epistemic modality. Palmer notes that Lyons suggests a theoretical

¹²⁷ Palmer, *Mood and Modality*, 1–3. Note that languages with robust subjunctives also have modal constructions, but they don't affect our analysis. The *realis/irrealis* distinction is the standard typological framework for non-Indo-European languages, where the concept of the subjunctive has no equivalent morphological instantiation.

¹²⁸ Derrida, *Cinders*, 37. "Il y a là cendre: il y a lieu."

objective epistemic modality but that it's contrived.¹²⁹ And while some non-Indo-European languages, such as Tuyuca, Serrano, and Central Pomo, offer complex evidential morphologies, they still require marking the speaker's evidential relationship to the statement.

Modality, the broader grammatical domain that encompasses mood categories like the subjunctive and modal systems like the English auxiliary verbs, is what Hartman marshals here. Alongside it, the middle voice, and possibly the infinitive can help us approach a *least wrong* speech. I will discuss the epistemic modes, including the subjunctive that Hartman has raised, while pointing to the middle voice and infinitive for further research. Whether languages with more robust mood morphology navigate this subject-centering more successfully than English remains an open question, and one with implications beyond the scope of this thesis.

Three available grammatical registers — the indicative, the epistemic modality of the irrealis family Hartman invokes, and free indirect discourse — each fail to capture what Hartman is reaching for. The indicative is unavailable from the outset: it asserts what occurred, and what occurred to Venus beyond her death is precisely what the archive has foreclosed. It is the doubly agentive language of white supremacy; it asserts knowledge of facts, “I assert (that I know) that John went to the store”. Even when that knowledge is not knowledge of what happened, it presents itself as outside and all-knowing, attempting to close the archive. “I assert (that I know) that X was recorded or was not recorded (and there's nothing more to say).” But as was shown in Chapter 2, there is no meta-archive. There is no view from nowhere, outside of history, from which we can say “this was not recorded (and nothing else can be said)”. The subjunctive takes

¹²⁹ Palmer, *Mood and Modality*, 33.

us out of the indicative mood, but only into the irrealis family, where the difficulties are different but no less real.

The irrealis family of grammatical structures—the subjunctive, the irrealis modals, and the epistemic system—fails for two structural reasons. First, we are stuck in language communicating about *what we know* about the past, rather than about *what was*. There is no way to characterize Venus’s being linguistically, we can only characterize *our own* epistemic uncertainty about her. There are no linguistic ontological modes; Palmer's exhaustive taxonomy of modality encompasses epistemic, evidential, deontic, and dynamic modality, but no ontological category.¹³⁰ Second, we are forced to speak in the present. Even in the indicative past or future, we speak in the present, when we say “John will go to the store” or “John went to the store”, we are indicating “I assert (that I know) that John will go to the store”, or “I assert (that I know) that John went to the store”, we are characterizing our impressions in the present. In the irrealis family of structures, tense isn’t even used to show time, it’s used to show a ‘distance’ from certainty (“John should have arrived”, “John will have arrived”), this is why the epistemic modals always anchor judgment in the present.¹³¹ However, Derrida tells us that the archive is neither operating in the present, nor in the past, it is operating towards the *future*, and, consistent with Hartman, “the *very possibility of knowledge* [is] suspended in the conditional”: “*if it is at all knowable*”.¹³²

¹³⁰ Palmer, *Mood and Modality*, 7–11, 22.

¹³¹ See Palmer, *Mood and Modality*, 33.

¹³² Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 37, 71.

There is no epistemic future modal construction in English that doesn't already imply counterfactuality—the only non-counterfactual option is the indicative future, which asserts rather than speculates. At least within English there are no alternatives. When we say that speaking about what might have been collapses into a present judgment (see Palmer above), we mean that a proposition can be in the past, but not the judgement (in epistemic modality), for example, we can say “She may have left by now” but not “Yesterday she might leave.”¹³³ And if we attempt to get around this—to represent a past subject's epistemic state as genuinely theirs rather than collapsing it into our own present judgment—we are driven toward free indirect discourse. Free indirect discourse appears to offer a way around these two problems but fails for a different reason. In ordinary reported speech, the reporting frame (“she thought that...”) distances the character's judgment and re-anchors it to the narrator's present. Free indirect discourse drops that frame entirely: instead of “John thought that Mary would be there by now,” we get simply “Mary would be there by now”—grammatically the narrator's sentence, but carrying the character's judgment, her sense of now, her inferential position. The character's perspective is preserved precisely because the sentence retains the markers of her viewpoint—the “now”, the “would”—but the markers of reported speech are omitted.¹³⁴ But this preservation comes at a price. Free indirect discourse requires inhabiting the consciousness of the subject of discourse, but Venus's consciousness is precisely what the archive has annihilated. To narrate from within her perspective is to fabricate that perspective, however sympathetically.

¹³³ Palmer, *Mood and Modality*, 33. “the proposition can be in the past, but the modality (the judgment) cannot”. (Dynamic modals can be in the past, e.g. “I could have gone”, but they are not relevant here, see Palmer, 15—even here we might consider the recognition of ability to be in the present).

¹³⁴ Palmer, *Mood and Modality*, 33. Admitting that “literary language” can appear to have the modality in the past but “[t]his is essentially reported speech ... with the verb of reporting ‘understood’.)”

The Hauntology in Hartman

Hartman goes beyond the subjunctive she invokes. The grammatical analysis above shows why no mood is fully adequate: the epistemic modal anchors judgment in the speaking subject, the indicative asserts what cannot be asserted, and free indirect discourse improperly attempts to step into Venus's head, doing further violence and sliding into fiction. What Hartman is doing in the conditional perfect and future perfect is less a matter of choosing the best available option and more like performing the inadequacy of all options while remaining within language.

This is the 'hauntological irrealis', introduced above. It's an extension of the grammatical irrealis into the realm of what language cannot directly provide. It's a way of approaching the grammar for events whose occurrence the archive attests to, but whose content is irrecoverable. They are neither present nor absent. Venus was there, but the grammar can say nothing in the indicative about her, and it cannot speculate honestly in epistemic modes. At its limit, it may be able to hold a place open, mark a lacuna, without presuming to substitute anything for it.

This is not simple speculation about what might have been. It's an acknowledgment of the unfillable space created by what was never recorded. When Hartman writes of Venus, "[t]he girl 'never will have any existence outside the precarious domicile of words' that allowed her to be murdered," the future perfect is not pointing to a completion but to a space in the archive that will always remain open. The archive's promissory structure, always oriented towards the future, is turned against itself.¹³⁵ The promise is kept, though it does not deliver a narration of a life but the trace of the violence that silenced it.

¹³⁵ Derrida, *Archive Fever*, 29. The archive's structure includes a promise to deliver to the future. See Chapter 2 on the archive.

Hartman's critical fabulation therefore cites the silence, rather than filling it as other grammatical constructions would do. She does this in the very same sense established in Chapter 2. To cite something is to lift it from its prior context and set it down in a new, radically different context, without erasing its origin. Hartman iterates the space in the archive, giving it a name, and orienting it toward future readers of the archive. Those future readers will not encounter a narrative about Venus, but the shape of a negative space. The citational act transforms what was irretrievable into what we might call the 'archived-unrecoverable'. This is what it means to put a silence in quotation marks—" "—to cite it out of the context the archive imposed and into one that exposes the violence rather than reinscribing it. What the archive previously ignored it now archives as lost. This forces the archive to point to its own violence that caused the loss.

This chapter opened with Benjamin's question: "are we not touched by the same breath of air which was among that which came before?" Hartman's response to silences is one answer to how we might speak honestly of that breath: neither pretending it wasn't there, as the archive did before Hartman engaged with it, nor claiming to have heard it, but noting that the breath that touched us points out a space it once moved through and acknowledging what it cost.

* * *

The authorizing norms of Euro-Western historiography produce silences through violence that cannot be undone from within those norms. Trouillot maps where silences enter; Derrida and Butler show those norms to be constitutive boundary-work, not neutral method. Hartman's critical fabulation demonstrates a practice that cites the silence rather than filling it. The hauntological irrealis names the register in which this becomes possible.

Through the girl known to us as Venus we see that silences enter at each moment; white supremacy and chattel slavery create and enforce those silences, and white supremacy reiterates and reinscribes them over centuries, establishing authorizing norms that prohibit us from speaking of her beyond the little that is already written, written to benefit her murderers. But the authorizing norms can never fix meaning, which is always subject to citation in another context. The norms of white supremacy inscribe an inside that has Venus and the violences done to her, both physical and historical, as its constitutive outside. By citing what the archive fails to show—the absences, silences, in the archive—Hartman forces the archive to point back onto itself, its silences, and the violences that created them. Hartman's grammar refuses the authorizing norms' indicative, which has nothing else to say about Venus; the speculation of the pure grammatical irrealis; and free indirect discourse's fictional move into Venus's head. In doing so, it navigates a path along the limits of what language can say, and along the boundary of the inside and its constitutive outside.

Hauntology is the spectral that haunts being; it is what ontology tries to exorcise. It extends ontology to the limits of the possibility of being. The hauntological irrealis is a mode that extends the grammatical irrealis to the limits of linguistic possibility; it gestures at a grammar that does not exist, a grammar for events which occurred, but whose content the

archive has rendered irrecoverable. From within the authorizing norms, this appears as transgression of methodology but is a theoretically grounded response to the structure of historical production. The hauntological irrealis is also a mode of textual accountability *to the silenced*; it opposes the indicative's accountability to evidentiary norms.

Hartman's work serves as an existence proof for transgressive historiography. The hauntological irrealis may also function within diverse transgressive historiographic practices—queer historiography, Indigenous historiography, disability historiography—and these remain to be examined.

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VITA

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